

**FOOD, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURES TO TACKLE EMERGING PRIORITIES**

Deliverable 6.1

Gap analysis and technology needs

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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FHERITALE GAP ANALYSIS AND TECHNOLOGY NEEDS

The FHERITALE project addresses the growing scientific, technological and societal challenges associated with artificial materials - such as micro- and nanoplastics, bioplastics, plastic additives and metallic particles - across food systems, human health and the environment. These challenges are inherently cross-domain and require coordinated access to advanced analytical services, interoperable data infrastructures and harmonised methodologies. Based on 168 responses to an online survey and additional input gathered during a co-creation workshop, the project has taken the first steps towards identifying priority research and service needs, assessing the readiness of existing technologies and highlighting gaps and barriers that limit their effective use in the food, health and environment domains.

PRIORITY NEEDS

Overall, the distribution of priorities reveals a **strong convergence around a limited set of cross-cutting needs**. A clear hierarchy of concerns lies in the Food and Environment domain (*environmental fate and degradation*, and *sustainable and functional food packaging*) while *Standardization of protocols*, *access to infrastructure*, and *One Health assessment* are consistent cross-domain needs.

TECHNOLOGY AND SERVICES READINESS

Perceived readiness levels emerging from the survey. It builds on the FHERITALE Service Readiness Classification: A) Fully operational and accessible services; B) Available but with limitations; C) Emerging or experimental technologies. The values obtained through desk-based analysis and validated by the RIs are reported on the right (see [zenodo.15554665](https://zenodo.org/record/15554665)). The average perceived readiness index points to **gaps in knowledge and visibility** rather than to a lack of underlying capabilities.

ADDRESSING NEEDS WITH SERVICES

Respondents prioritise **support and training, ease of access, and cost-effectiveness** as the most important features of a new service. These aspects were consistently more important than interoperability or regulatory relevance.

This outcome informs that even mature technologies may fail to generate impact if not embedded within accessible, well-supported and economically viable service models.

GAPS, BARRIERS AND DOMAINS

Taken together, the gap and barrier results suggest that the service ecosystem required by FHERITALE is constrained by a combination of **structural limitations** (access and cost) and **system-level enablers** (knowledge, validation, and interoperability). These findings indicate that service development should not focus only on adding “new techniques”, but also on strengthening the conditions that allow techniques to function as reliable services across Europe.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

CLUSTER SUGGESTIONS: INTEGRATED SERVICE SOLUTIONS

The survey results highlight that shared needs are connected not with individual technologies, many of which are already well-established, but with integrating them into end-to-end services that address complex, cross-domain needs. This document provides a strong rationale for developing service clusters understood as coordinated sets of infrastructures, tools, expertise, and support functions that can respond to these needs collectively.

ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING

Scope: Detection of MNPs, fate & degradation, environmental impact
Technologies: FTIR, LC-MS, imaging tools
Users: RIs, regulatory agencies, EU projects

ANALYTICAL & CHARACTERISATION SERVICES

Scope: Chemical analysis, spectrometry, material characterisation
Technologies: LC-MS, FTIR, ICP-MS
Users: Industry, RIs, regulators

TOXICOLOGY & EXPOSURE MODELLING

Scope: PBPK, in vivo/in vitro, One Health assessment
Technologies: PBPK modelling, in vivo tox, omics integrations
Users: Academia, RIs, regulators

BIOLOGICAL MODELS & IN-VITRO SYSTEMS

Scope: Organoids, ex vivo assays, 3D systems
Technologies: 3D organoids, placental perfusion, ex vivo platforms
Users: Reasearch groups, RIs, EU consortia

DATA INTEROPERABILITY & DIGITAL TOOLS

Scope: Image analysis, data integration, FAIR pipelines
Technologies: Digital analysis, AI tools, interoperable platforms
Users: All stakeholder groups

SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING & FUNCTIONAL MATERIALS

Scope: Eco-fuctional materials, circularity, functional properties
Technologies: Material testing, chemical profiling
Users: Industry, academia, RIs

1. Executive summary

The FHERITALE project addresses the growing scientific, technological and societal challenges associated with artificial materials - such as micro- and nanoplastics, bioplastics, plastic additives and metallic particles - across food systems, human health and the environment. These challenges are inherently cross-domain and require coordinated access to advanced analytical services, interoperable data infrastructures and harmonised methodologies. Within this context, Work Package 6 (WP6 - *Thematic landscape and gap analysis*) plays a key role by providing a structured, evidence-based assessment of existing gaps and emerging technology needs, laying the foundation for future service development, coordination and roadmap definition.

This deliverable, D6.1 - *Gap Analysis and Technology Needs*, presents the results of a comprehensive gap analysis conducted through a co-creation-driven process involving research infrastructures (RIs), academic institutions, regulatory bodies, industry stakeholders and sister projects operating in the Food-Health-Environment nexus. The analysis builds upon the mapping and categorisation of services and technologies performed in WP5 (*Enabling selected priorities*), and in particular the outcome of Deliverable D5.1 - *Categorization of services and technologies*, complementing it with a user-centred perspective that explicitly addresses unmet needs, readiness limitations and systemic barriers. While WP5 provides a structured inventory of existing services and their maturity, D6.1 focuses on *how these services are perceived, accessed and used by the community, and where critical gaps still remain*.

The methodology adopted in WP6 combines qualitative and quantitative approaches and is explicitly grounded in co-creation principles. It includes:

- i) an online Focus Group aimed at validating the gap analysis framework and the Service Readiness Classification (SRC) methodology
- ii) a large-scale online survey collecting structured feedback from 168 respondents across multiple stakeholder categories
- iii) an in-person co-creation workshop held in Bucharest in October 2025, designed to validate preliminary findings, refine priorities, discuss systemic barriers and initiate the discussion on thematic clustering and future service evolution.

The results highlight a strong convergence of needs around environmental monitoring and degradation processes, standardisation and protocol harmonisation, and access to research infrastructures and advanced analytical capabilities. While several mature technologies, such as Fourier Transform InfraRed spectroscopy (FTIR), mass spectrometry and sequencing platforms, are already operational, many services remain partially aligned with user needs or constrained by limited accessibility, lack of validation, or insufficient interoperability, as well as recurring issues discussed by stakeholders in relation to detection capabilities and exposure/dosimetry assessment. Emerging approaches, including advanced biological models, Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic modelling (PBPK) and integrated One Health assessment frameworks, are recognised as strategically important but still face significant readiness and feasibility challenges.

Beyond the identification of gaps, the analysis also reveals clear patterns linking priority needs to specific categories of barriers, including limited access to RIs and their services, validation deficits, fragmented data ecosystems and regulatory constraints. These insights provide the analytical basis for defining clustering criteria and for structuring thematic groups of services and actors, as foreseen in Task 6.2 (*Definition of the Thematic Clusters*). While the formal definition and validation of thematic clusters will be addressed in the subsequent WP6 deliverable (D6.2), this report already establishes the conceptual and empirical foundations for that process, informed by the outcomes of the focus group and the Bucharest workshop.

By prioritising needs according to importance, urgency and feasibility, this deliverable provides a structured basis for subsequent activities in WP7 (*Service coordination and development*) and WP8 (*Roadmapping and sustainability*). In this sense, D6.1 functions as a key integrative step between the descriptive mapping of existing capacities (WP5) and the forward-looking definition of coordinated services, clusters and roadmaps foreseen in the later work packages. Ultimately, D6.1 contributes to shaping a coherent and user-driven service landscape within FHERITALE, supporting evidence-based decision-making, strategic alignment across domains, and long-term integration across European research infrastructures.

2. Introduction

The rapid increase in the production, use and environmental dissemination of artificial materials has introduced a new level of complexity for scientific research, regulatory assessment and technological innovation. Materials such as micro- and nanoplastics, bioplastics, plastic additives and engineered particles are now routinely detected across food systems, biological tissues and environmental compartments. Their presence raises pressing questions regarding exposure pathways, the long-term effects on human and ecosystem health, and the cumulative impact of chronic, low-level contamination.

Addressing these challenges requires far more than the availability of individual analytical techniques or isolated research capabilities. It calls for a coordinated and integrated service ecosystem able to support interdisciplinary research across food, health and environmental domains, in line with a One Health perspective. Such an ecosystem must combine advanced analytical and modelling tools with harmonised protocols, interoperable data infrastructures, and equitable access to research infrastructures. Without this coordination, scientific knowledge risks remaining fragmented, difficult to compare and ultimately insufficient to inform evidence-based decision-making. In practical terms, this fragmentation affects not only the comparability of scientific results, but also the capacity of regulators, industry and research actors to rely on shared evidence when designing policies, assessing risks or developing innovative solutions. Bridging these gaps requires coordinated efforts that go beyond individual projects or infrastructures.

Within this broader context, the FHERITALE project has been conceived to contribute to a more coherent European research landscape for the study of artificial materials and their impacts. Building on the strengths of several major Research Infrastructures and engaging a wide community of stakeholders, the project aims to facilitate access to high-level services while fostering cross-domain integration and long-term sustainability. WP6 plays a central role in this effort by explicitly focusing on the identification of gaps between existing capabilities and emerging research and service needs.

While previous work packages - most notably WP5 - have concentrated on mapping and categorising available services and technologies, WP6 deliberately shifts the analytical perspective. Rather than asking solely *what exists*, it seeks to understand *what is missing*, *what remains inaccessible*, and *what is not yet ready to be used effectively by the research and stakeholder communities*. This shift from a supply-driven to a user- and need-driven approach is essential for ensuring that future service development is grounded in real-world demands and constraints. Such an approach acknowledges that technological availability alone does not guarantee effective uptake. Factors such as access conditions, costs, required expertise, regulatory acceptance and data interoperability play a decisive role in determining whether a service can be realistically used by different communities

The scope of this deliverable, D6.1 – *Gap Analysis and Technology Needs*, is therefore twofold. First, it aims to provide a comprehensive and structured analysis of gaps, grounded in direct input from a diverse range of stakeholders, including Research Infrastructures, academic

institutions, regulatory bodies, industry representatives and “sister” projects with complementary objectives. This analysis goes beyond a simple listing of missing technologies, addressing also systemic and cross-cutting barriers such as limited access to infrastructures, lack of standardisation, insufficient validation, and fragmented data ecosystems.

Second, D6.1 seeks to translate this gap analysis into a prioritised set of emerging needs, explicitly considering dimensions such as importance, urgency and feasibility. This prioritisation is a critical step in moving from descriptive analysis towards actionable outcomes. By distinguishing between needs that are already technically mature but organisationally constrained, and those that are strategically relevant but still at an early stage of development, the deliverable supports informed decision-making and targeted investment.

Importantly, D6.1 does not aim to duplicate or replace the extensive inventory of technologies and services developed within WP5 and documented in D5.1. On the contrary, it builds directly upon that work, using the categorisation framework and the Service Readiness Classification (SRC) as a shared reference point. The added value of WP6 lies in the integration of qualitative insights, cross-domain perspectives and co-creation dynamics, which allow for a deeper understanding of how technologies are actually used, perceived and constrained in practice.

This qualitative dimension is particularly relevant in a field characterised by rapid technological evolution and heterogeneous user communities. Differences in disciplinary cultures, regulatory environments, and institutional capacities mean that the same technology can be perceived as fully operational in one context and largely inaccessible in another. Capturing these nuances requires direct engagement with users and stakeholders, as well as iterative validation of assumptions and analytical frameworks.

Finally, this deliverable is explicitly positioned as a bridge between analytical mapping and future-oriented action within the FHERITALE project. The outcomes presented in D6.1 provide essential input for subsequent activities in WP7, which focuses on the coordination and development of services, and in WP8, which addresses roadmap definition and long-term sustainability. By linking identified gaps and prioritised needs to potential service evolution and clustering, WP6 contributes to shaping a coherent, user-driven and strategically aligned service landscape. By explicitly capturing these dimensions, WP6 contributes to a more realistic and practice-oriented understanding of the current service landscape. This understanding is essential to avoid the development of services that are technically advanced but misaligned with user needs, or that remain underutilised due to structural or organisational constraints.

In this sense, D6.1 represents a key milestone in the transition from understanding the current landscape to actively designing the future of integrated research services in the Food–Health–Environment nexus. It lays the conceptual and empirical foundation upon which coordinated actions, shared investments and long-term collaborations can be built within and beyond the FHERITALE consortium.

3. Methodological framework and co-creation process

3.1 Rationale and overall methodological approach

The methodological framework adopted for Task 6.1 (*Gap analysis*) has been designed to ensure that the gap analysis and identification of technology needs are robust, inclusive and directly grounded in the experience of users and stakeholders. Given the cross-domain nature of the challenges addressed by FHERITALE, a purely desk-based or technology-centred assessment would have been insufficient to capture the diversity of needs, constraints and expectations characterising the Food-Health-Environment nexus. For this reason, WP6 follows a **co-creation-driven methodology**, combining structured data collection with iterative qualitative engagement and validation, as defined within milestone MS8 - *Gap analysis procedures defined*. The approach explicitly integrated multiple perspectives and was inclusive by design, deliberately structured to involve a wide and balanced range of actors. These included FHERITALE project partners, representatives of RIs operating across the food, health and environmental domains, sister projects addressing related scientific and technological challenges, as well as external stakeholders such as industry actors, technology developers and applied research organisations. This broad participation ensured that the analysis captured not only scientific and technical perspectives, but also operational, regulatory and market-oriented considerations. This diversity of inputs is essential to avoid sector-specific bias and to ensure that the resulting analysis reflects real-world conditions rather than idealised service models. The methodological design builds upon and complements the analytical work performed in WP5. While WP5 focused on mapping and categorising existing services and technologies, WP6 moves one step further by assessing how those services are perceived, accessed and used, and by identifying where mismatches exist between availability and actual research or innovation needs.

The overall methodology is structured around **three interlinked components**, implemented sequentially but iteratively:

1. Qualitative dialogue and validation, through an online Focus Group and targeted consultations
2. Structured quantitative data collection, through a large-scale online survey
3. Interactive validation and refinement, through an in-person co-creation workshop.

This combination allows the analysis to evolve progressively, moving from conceptual validation to broad-based evidence collection and finally to collective interpretation and refinement.

Figure 1 provides a schematic representation of the WP6 methodological framework and illustrates the iterative nature of the process, integrating qualitative validation, structured survey data collection and interactive stakeholder engagement.

Fig.1. Overview of the WP6 methodological framework.

Each step contributes to progressively refining the understanding of user needs, barriers and readiness levels, with the overarching objective of informing service clustering and coordination. The framework is designed to move from evidence collection (survey and workshops) to structured analysis and actionable outputs, supporting the definition of thematic clusters and service concepts in subsequent tasks

3.2 Qualitative dialogue through Focus Group

An online Focus Group, held on 30 June 2025 and co-organised by ENEA and IBA, represented the first formal step of the WP6 methodology. Its primary objective was not to generate results per se, but to validate the analytical framework underpinning the gap analysis before launching the large-scale survey.

Specifically, the Focus Group aimed to:

- Validate the proposed gap analysis structure, including the definition of priority domains and priority needs
- Assess the clarity, relevance and completeness of the Service Readiness Classification (SRC) framework
- Review and refine the semi-structured questionnaire, ensuring that questions were understandable, meaningful and applicable across different stakeholder groups.

By front-loading this validation step, WP6 ensured that the subsequent survey would be based on a shared understanding of key concepts, reducing ambiguity and improving the quality and comparability of responses. This early validation phase was deliberately designed to reduce the risk of conceptual misalignment across stakeholder groups and domains. By openly discussing definitions, assumptions and analytical boundaries at an early stage, the Focus Group helped establish a common interpretative framework that would later underpin the survey-based data

collection. This approach was particularly important given the heterogeneous nature of the targeted communities and the cross-domain scope of the analysis.

The Focus Group brought together a carefully selected group of participants representing a broad range of perspectives. Participants included:

- Representatives of major European RIs active in food, health and environmental domains
- External advisors from national and European agencies
- Academic experts from universities and research centres
- Representatives of ongoing and completed EU-funded projects relevant to artificial materials
- Industry-facing stakeholders with experience in applied research and service utilisation.

In total, the Focus Group involved experts representing both consortium partners (13 participants, covering all project's Beneficiaries) and external organisations (11 participants), ensuring a balanced mix of internal project knowledge and independent, external perspectives. This balance was considered essential to avoid self-referential assessments and to challenge implicit assumptions emerging from within the consortium. This heterogeneous composition allowed for constructive discussion across disciplinary and institutional boundaries, highlighting differences in expectations and constraints that might otherwise remain implicit.

The Focus Group was conducted online using the Zoom Workplace platform (2025 Zoom Communications, Inc., Version 1.34.1.11535) utilizing the integrated Zoom Whiteboard tool to facilitate real-time visual collaboration among participants and visual structuring of inputs.

A summary of the Focus Group structure and stakeholder composition, together with the full agenda and discussion blocks are reported in Annex 1.

The Focus Group resulted in several important refinements to the WP6 methodology, including:

- Clarification of SRC definitions through concrete examples
- Inclusion of additional explanatory notes for complex technologies
- Expansion of free-text fields in the survey to capture contextual insights
- Improved alignment of priority needs with industry and regulatory perspectives.

These refinements were directly incorporated into the final version of the questionnaire, ensuring that the survey instrument was both comprehensive and user-friendly.

Overall, the Focus Group confirmed the robustness of the proposed methodology while highlighting the importance of flexibility, contextualisation and clear communication when addressing heterogeneous stakeholder communities. This validation step was instrumental in strengthening the methodological foundation of WP6 before moving to large-scale data collection.

Following the Focus Group session, a series of targeted follow-up interactions were conducted with the external participants, including email exchanges and bilateral online meetings. These additional consultations focused on clarifying specific questions, refining terminology, and testing the practical usability of the draft questionnaire across different stakeholder profiles. This iterative post-session exchange further contributed to the consolidation of the final survey

instrument, ensuring clarity, inclusiveness and technical consistency prior to its large-scale dissemination.

3.3 Structured data collection through the online survey

Following the Focus Group, a semi-structured online survey was developed and implemented using LimeSurvey (LimeSurvey GmbH, Version 4.6.3+210518; <https://survey.metrofood.eu/index.php/826343>). The survey was designed to collect both **quantitative and qualitative data**, combining closed questions with open-text fields to capture nuanced perspectives. The questionnaire was finalised after an iterative refinement process, incorporating feedback received during the Focus Group as well as additional clarifications gathered through follow-up exchanges with selected participants, as specified in Section 3.2.

The questionnaire addressed the following main areas:

- Priority research and service needs across domains
- Technologies currently in use and those perceived as critical but inaccessible
- Service Readiness Classification (SRC) for a selected set of technologies
- Types of gaps and barriers limiting service uptake
- Suggestions for future services and improvements.

The survey was launched the 1st of September 2025 and remained open for 2 months to maximise participation across different geographical regions and institutional contexts. It disseminated through multiple channels, including the FHERITALE website (<https://fheritale.eu/gap-analysis-questionnaire>) and FHERITALE partner networks, Beneficiaries and RIs' websites and mailing lists, sister projects, the ERIC Forum website (<https://www.eric-forum.eu/2025/10/14/take-part-in-this-story-the-fheritale-survey/>), the EU Food Safety Platform (<https://foodsafetyplatform.eu/news/fheritale-survey-of-research-support-services/>), direct professional contacts, the networks of the participants to the focus group. In addition, the survey was actively promoted during relevant scientific and stakeholder-facing events attended by project partners, including international conferences and workshops in the food, health and environmental measurement communities (e.g., National Workshop of the National Research and Development Institutes, at ICAM – UVT, Timisoara (Romania) – 3 Sept. 2025; 8th International IMEKOFOODS Conference, Ljubljana (Slovenia) – 22-24 Sept. 2025; EMN-Food General Assembly, Ljubljana (Slovenia) – 25 Sept. 2025; Conference “Food Safety First: Building a One Health Approach to Safer Food Systems”. Online – 21 Nov. 2025). This broad dissemination strategy was essential to reach stakeholders beyond the immediate consortium.

In total, 168 responses were collected, representing a wide spectrum of stakeholder categories, disciplines and geographical contexts. Respondents included RI operators, academic researchers, industry representatives, regulators and project managers. Participation covered both actors directly involved in service provision and users of scientific services, ensuring that the dataset reflects both supply- and demand-side perspectives. This diversity contributes significantly to the robustness of the dataset, allowing for cross-cutting analysis and

stakeholder-specific segmentation. Importantly, respondents were not required to answer all questions, reducing response fatigue and increasing the quality of individual answers. This design choice proved particularly effective for technically complex sections, such as SRC assessment and gap categorisation, where respondents could contribute selectively based on their expertise and experience.

An overview of survey respondents, highlighting the representation by organisation type, country, age range and active involvement in RI initiatives, along with the full text of the questionnaire, including all questions and response options, is provided in Annex II.

The analysis of survey responses and the synthesis of quantitative and qualitative results are presented in Section 4, where emerging gaps and technology needs are systematically described and prioritised.

3.4 Interactive validation through the Bucharest co-creation workshop

The in-person workshop held in Bucharest on 22-23 October 2025, organised by IBA with the contribution of ENEA, represented the final methodological step of Task 6.1 (<https://bioresurse.ro/en/blogs/media/workshop-pheritale-project-from-mapping-to-action-a-co-creation-pathway-towards-gap-identification-and-thematic-clustering-22-23-octombrie>).

While the Focus Group served primarily to validate the analytical framework and the survey design, the Bucharest workshop aimed at consolidating it, testing its robustness through the analysis of preliminary replies, and collectively interpreting their strategic implications. Unlike previous steps, which relied mainly on remote interaction, the workshop created a shared physical space for dialogue, allowing for collective interpretation, richer exchanges, informal discussion, and deeper reflection on complex or potentially controversial issues. This face-to-face setting proved particularly valuable for addressing cross-domain challenges, where differences in terminology, expectations and operational constraints often require direct interaction to be fully understood.

The workshop aimed to four main objectives:

- Create a shared understanding of the broader service and research landscape through direct exchange among stakeholders
- Present and critically discuss the preliminary insights from the online survey
- Validate and, where necessary, refine the priority needs and gaps identified through quantitative and qualitative analysis
- Explore the implications of these findings for future service clustering, coordination and strategic actions within FHERITALE.

In this sense, the workshop functioned as a **collective sense-making exercise**, transforming individual survey responses and analytical outputs into shared interpretations and strategic orientations. Rather than seeking consensus, the workshop explicitly aimed to surface areas of convergence as well as points of divergence, uncertainty or tension between stakeholder perspectives.

The workshop was structured as a full-day event, combining plenary sessions with interactive co-creation sessions. It brought together a total of 26 participants from diverse groups, including:

- representatives of FHERITALE consortium partners
- operators and managers of RIs active in food, health and environmental domains
- representatives of external RIs and metrology institutes
- stakeholders from national and European agencies
- representatives of EU-funded projects and sister initiatives relevant to artificial materials, packaging and traceability.

The complete agenda of the workshop and details on participants are provided in Annex III.

The outcomes of the Bucharest workshop were systematically cross-checked against the survey results and the earlier Focus Group findings. This triangulation allowed for validation, refinement and contextualisation of the identified gaps and needs, ensuring that final conclusions were supported by multiple sources of evidence.

Importantly, the workshop also marked a clear transition point within WP6. While Task 6.1 focuses on gap analysis and prioritisation, the discussions explicitly opened the way towards Task 6.2, addressing clustering criteria, actor mapping and the translation of needs into potential service concepts.

The workshop outputs therefore fed directly into:

- the final interpretation of gaps and technology needs presented in this deliverable
- the preliminary definition of thematic clusters
- the alignment of WP6 results with the planning activities of WP7 and WP8.

In this way, the Bucharest co-creation workshop not only validated past analytical work but also actively shaped the forward-looking orientation of the FHERITALE project, reinforcing the continuity between evidence generation, strategic planning and service development. It also contributed to the achievement of Milestone MS9 - *“Map & Thematic cluster” focus group and map of actors and approaches validated*, by providing a shared space for validating emerging thematic areas, stakeholder perspectives and preliminary clustering logics

3.5 Methodological considerations: strengths, limitations and added value

The methodological approach adopted within WP6 has been deliberately designed to balance analytical robustness with openness to stakeholder perspectives, recognising the complexity and heterogeneity of the Food–Health–Environment nexus addressed by the FHERITALE project. The combination of qualitative and quantitative tools, implemented through an iterative and co-creation-oriented process, represents one of the key strengths of Task 6.1.

A first major strength lies in the coverage and diversity of stakeholder engagement. By involving Research Infrastructures, academic researchers, regulatory bodies, industry actors, technology developers and representatives of sister projects, the methodology ensured that no single disciplinary or institutional perspective dominated the analysis. This diversity was essential to capture differences in expectations, constraints and levels of maturity across

domains, and to reflect the reality that technologies and services may be perceived very differently depending on context and user group.

A second strength concerns the combination of in-depth qualitative insights with a wide quantitative dataset, enabling comparisons across disciplines, stakeholder categories and application contexts. The Focus Group and the Bucharest workshop provided space for open discussion, contextual interpretation and collective sense-making, while the large-scale online survey offered structured evidence from a broad respondent base. This combination allowed emerging patterns to be identified and tested against concrete experiences, reducing the risk of anecdotal conclusions and strengthening the overall credibility of the findings.

The iterative validation process represents a further added value. Key concepts, such as priority needs, types of gaps and the Service Readiness Classification (SRC), were not imposed a priori but progressively refined through stakeholder feedback. This iterative approach helped to reduce conceptual ambiguity, improve the clarity of analytical tools and ensure that the final survey instrument was understandable and meaningful across different communities.

At the same time, some methodological limitations should be acknowledged. Participation levels inevitably varied across domains and stakeholder categories, reflecting differences in community size, engagement capacity and perceived relevance of the topic. Certain highly specialised or emerging technologies remain under-represented in the dataset, not due to lack of importance, but because of their niche character and limited user base. Moreover, as participation in the survey was voluntary and not all questions were mandatory, the depth of information varies across sections.

These limitations are, however, intrinsic to exploratory and co-creation-based methodologies and do not undermine the validity of the results. On the contrary, they are addressed through transparency and triangulation of evidence across the different sources and highlight areas where further engagement and targeted investigation may be required.

Ethical and data protection considerations were fully integrated into the methodological design. The online survey explicitly informed participants that the data collected would be used exclusively for the purposes of the FHERITALE project. Providing personal information was optional, and any personal data voluntarily supplied were treated confidentially and stored in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). By submitting the questionnaire, respondents provided informed consent to the processing of their responses for project-related research and analysis.

Similarly, informed consent procedures were applied for both the online Focus Group and the in-person Bucharest workshop. Participants were informed in advance about the objectives of the activities, the use of aggregated and anonymised information in public project outputs, and the recording or documentation of sessions for internal analysis purposes. This transparent approach ensured compliance with ethical standards while fostering an open and trust-based environment for discussion.

Overall, the WP6 methodology provides a solid, transparent and user-centred foundation for the gap analysis presented in this deliverable. By grounding the identification and prioritisation of needs in lived research and innovation practices, it ensures that the outcomes of D6.1 are not

abstract or purely technology-driven, but directly relevant to the communities that FHERITALE aims to support. This methodological robustness is essential for enabling the effective translation of results into subsequent activities on service coordination, clustering and roadmapping within WP7 and WP8.

4. Results of the Gap Analysis and Identification of Technology Needs

The results presented in this section are based on the analysis of 168 responses collected through the WP6 online survey. The dataset represents a broad and heterogeneous community, including operators of Research Infrastructures, academic researchers, representatives of public bodies and regulatory agencies, industry stakeholders, technology developers, and coordinators of EU-funded projects.

Such diversity is particularly relevant in the context of FHERITALE, as the challenges associated with artificial materials span multiple scientific domains and application contexts. Rather than aiming for statistical representativeness in a strict sense, the survey was designed to capture informed and experience-based perspectives from actors directly involved in research, service provision, regulation and innovation, thereby providing a meaningful picture of perceived gaps, priorities and constraints as they are encountered in real research and operational settings.

Respondents were characterised by different roles within the research and innovation ecosystem, including both service providers and service users. This dual perspective allows the analysis to capture not only what services and technologies are available, but also how they are accessed, perceived and utilised in practice, and where mismatches between supply and demand persist. This distinction is particularly relevant in the context of RIs, where formal service availability does not always translate into effective accessibility or usability for end users.

The survey dataset includes both quantitative inputs, derived from closed questions with predefined answer options, and qualitative contributions, collected through open-text fields allowing respondents to contextualise their answers, provide examples, and highlight domain-specific issues. This mixed structure was deliberately adopted to balance comparability across responses with the need to capture nuanced insights that cannot be fully expressed through predefined categories. Open-text responses were particularly valuable in identifying cross-cutting barriers, contextual constraints and emerging needs not fully anticipated during the questionnaire design phase.

Survey results were not analysed in isolation. They were complemented and contextualised through the outcomes of the in-person co-creation workshop held in Bucharest, which provided an additional layer of qualitative validation and collective interpretation, as well as critical reflection of emerging trends. This collective discussion also allowed participants to reflect on

interdependencies between needs, technologies and organisational constraints that may not be evident from survey responses alone.

The analysis therefore combines:

- Quantitative aggregation of closed questions, including priority needs, SRC levels and types of gaps
- Qualitative interpretation of open-text responses, examples and comments provided by the respondents
- Cross-cutting comparisons across stakeholder categories, where relevant, to highlight convergences and divergences in needs and perceptions
- Qualitative triangulation with workshop discussions, used to validate, nuance and contextualise survey-based findings.

This mixed-method approach allows the analysis to go beyond a simple numerical ranking of needs or technologies. Instead, it supports a more nuanced reading of the results, where quantitative trends are interpreted in light of practical experience, institutional constraints and cross-domain interactions discussed during the workshop. In this way, the analysis aims to reflect not only what is considered important, but also what is considered feasible and actionable by the community.

Quantitative results were analysed using descriptive statistics, focusing on frequencies, distributions and average values, particularly for priority needs and SRC levels. Qualitative responses were reviewed and coded iteratively to identify recurring themes, emerging patterns and illustrative examples that support and enrich the quantitative findings.

Where appropriate, the analysis also considers differences and convergences across stakeholder categories, acknowledging that perceptions of needs and gaps may vary depending on institutional role, disciplinary background and level of involvement in service provision or use. These comparisons are intended to highlight complementarities and tensions, rather than to rank stakeholder perspectives. Such differences are treated as informative signals for service design and coordination, rather than inconsistencies to be resolved.

The results are presented in a progressive way, starting from priority needs, moving to technology readiness, and then addressing systemic gaps and barriers that limit effective service uptake. This structure mirrors the logic of the questionnaire itself and supports a coherent interpretation of how needs, technological maturity and structural constraints interact within the FHERITALE service landscape. Where relevant, insights emerging from the Bucharest workshop are used to corroborate or further explain survey findings.

Detailed results and thematic analyses are presented in the following subsections, while methodological choices related to survey design and data collection are previously described in Section 3.

4.1 Priority research and service needs across domains

The analysis of priority research and service needs constitutes the first and most central layer of the WP6 gap analysis, as it reflects the direct expectations and concerns expressed by the

FHERITALE stakeholder community. Respondents were asked to indicate which research and service areas they considered most critical in the context of artificial materials, micro- and nanoplastics, and related technologies across food, health and environmental domains.

Figure 2 presents the aggregated distribution of priority needs across all respondents selecting each research and service area. The results show a clear and consistent pattern, with a limited number of needs emerging as dominant across the dataset.

Environmental fate and degradation processes appear as the most frequently selected priority. This reflects a widespread concern regarding the persistence, transformation and accumulation of artificial materials in environmental compartments, as well as the limited availability of harmonised tools to study degradation pathways under realistic conditions. Respondents repeatedly emphasised the difficulty of linking laboratory-based results with environmental exposure scenarios, highlighting the need for services that bridge experimental data, modelling approaches and field observations.

With the same ranking, **sustainable and functional food packaging** emerges as a major priority. This result reflects both regulatory pressure and industrial demand for alternatives to conventional plastic materials, as well as scientific uncertainty regarding the performance, safety and life-cycle impacts of novel materials. The strong representation of this need confirms the relevance of FHERITALE's focus on food-related applications and underscores the importance of integrating material science, toxicology and environmental assessment within a shared service framework.

A third highly ranked need concerns the **standardisation and harmonisation of protocols**. The prominence of this issue across the survey indicates that many of the existing analytical and experimental capabilities are perceived as fragmented or insufficiently validated. Respondents frequently noted that the lack of shared protocols undermines data comparability, slows regulatory uptake and limits the transferability of results across laboratories and research infrastructures.

The **One Health assessment** approach also features prominently among the priority needs. This result highlights an increasing awareness of the interconnected nature of food safety, environmental contamination and human health impacts. Respondents expressed the need for integrative services capable of linking exposure data, biological effects and environmental monitoring within a single analytical framework, rather than treating these dimensions in isolation.

Finally, **access to research infrastructures and advanced analytical capabilities** represents a recurrent priority. Even where technologies are available in principle, many respondents reported difficulties related to access conditions, costs, geographical constraints or lack of visibility of existing services. This confirms that gaps are not limited to technological readiness but also include organisational and structural barriers that affect service uptake.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of domain-specific priority needs grouped according to the domains (Food, Health, Environment, and Cross-domain), while Figure 4 provides an heatmap aggregating the share of respondents (0–1 scale) within each domain who selected a given

priority research need. This view complements the individual histograms by highlighting where priorities are shared across domains and where they are distinct.

Fig.2. Overall priority research and service needs identified

Overall, the distribution of priorities reveals a strong convergence around a limited set of cross-cutting needs. These needs are not confined to a single domain or stakeholder group, but reflect shared challenges that cut across disciplines, institutional roles and application contexts. Importantly, the results suggest that stakeholders are not primarily calling for entirely new technologies, but rather for better integration, validation and accessibility of existing capabilities.

This convergence provides a robust basis for subsequent analysis of technology readiness and service gaps, as well as for the definition of thematic clusters that can address multiple needs simultaneously. At the same time, it highlights the importance of considering feasibility and implementation constraints, which are explored in the following subsections.

Fig.3. Priority needs across domains. Grouped horizontal bar chart show, for each need, the number of selections by domain (Food, Health, Environment, Cross-domain)

For “**Food domain**” a clear hierarchy of concerns centred on measurement reliability and market-facing innovation is shown. **Sustainable and functional food packaging** stands out as the foremost priority, selected by roughly 36 % of “Food” respondents. This is not simply a call for new materials: it reflects a need for the measurability of performance (migration, barrier properties, durability), safety (including potential micro- and nanoplastics release), and life-cycle impacts. Immediately adjacent, **Traceability and authenticity monitoring** (29 %) occupies the second rank, reflecting the Food community’s ongoing need to guarantee provenance and guard against adulteration, a topic that routinely demands consistent analytical workflows and shared reference datasets. The third tier is **Detection of MNPs in food** (26 %), which in turn relates to consumer safety and regulatory scrutiny. Two horizontal priorities run through the Food domain: **One Health assessment** and **Standardisation of protocols** (both 21 %). One Health frames food safety as inseparable from environmental and human health pathways, while standardisation acknowledges that innovation depends on reliable and comparable data. Overall, “Food” respondents are asking for co-developed methods, Reference Materials, and FAIR-by-design data practices. These would allow laboratories to evaluate novel packaging options and traceability solutions on a level analytical playing field, shortening the path from pilots to market adoption.

With a smaller sample (n = 19), the “**Health domain**” shows a triad of co-leaders: **Human exposure modelling**, **One Health assessment**, and **Access to infrastructure** (26% each). This

pattern points to a delivery chain in which measurements feed into exposure models and ultimately support risk assessment under a One Health umbrella. Crucially, it also underscores the need for **RI access** to high-end platforms and specialised assays without which these models cannot be calibrated or validated. Secondary signals include **Traceability/authenticity** and **Standardisation of protocols** (both 16%), reminding that health-oriented studies still rely on robust food chain data and comparable methods upstream. Taken together, the results for the Health domain call for: harmonised measurement protocols; curated, annotated datasets for model inputs; and accessible infrastructures for advanced analytics. The emphasis on One Health makes clear that stakeholders are not looking at exposure in isolation, but as part of cross-domain evidence chains that connect food production, environmental dispersion, and human outcomes.

The “Environment domain” is dominated by **Environmental fate and degradation** (33%), which reflects the long-standing need to understand persistence, transformation, and bioavailability across matrices (water, soil, air, biota). The second category is **Sustainable/functional packaging** (24%). At first glance that might seem more “food-oriented”, but the environmental cohort’s interest suggests a systems view: packaging innovation must be assessed in terms of environmental pathways and impacts, not only as product performance. In the same band is scored **Traceability/authenticity** and **One Health** (both 20%;), indicating a trend to stitch environmental evidence to food chain provenance and health outcomes. **Standardisation of protocols** (18%) emphasise reproducible sampling, harmonised analytical workflows, and inter-laboratory comparability. Operationally, the “Environment domain” results in a demand of **harmonised sampling, QA/QC schemes, and inter-laboratory comparisons** to elevate fate and degradation results to policy-ready evidence. It also suggests the need for a closer alignment with Food and Health datasets, so that environmental measurements are not siloed but can be re-used downstream in exposure modelling and risk framing.

Finally, despite its smaller size as a sample, the “**Cross-domain**” is remarkably decisive about enablers. Access to infrastructure represents a high priority (44%), followed by Environmental fate and degradation and Standardisation of protocols (both 38%). One Health and Cross-sectoral data integration (both 31%) complete the picture. In practice, respondents who explicitly act across domains underline that what they need most is capacity plus comparability plus connectivity all together. This means the ability to get onto platforms, use common SOPs, and integrate results across the food-environment-health nexus. This is both pragmatic and strategic: pragmatic, because without access and standardisation everything results fragmented; strategic, because integration is what turns local measurements into evidence chains that policy makers can trust. The results clearly suggest the need of: TNA/access schemes, community SOPs, and template data models that make cross-use possible by design.

Fig.4. Heatmap of the priority needs identified according to domains.

The heatmap visualises, for each domain, the share of respondents who selected a given research need (0–1 scale). Domains are shown on the columns, while rows list the needs ordered by their overall average share. Read row-wise to understand what each domain prioritises; read column-wise to see which needs are broadly cross-cutting vs. domain-specific.

The heatmap of Figure 4 compares these domain-related outcomes together, side by side, offering a consolidated perspective on where the domains converge and where they diverge. By plotting the share of selection within each domain, it becomes evident that some needs are widely shared, while others are domain-specific. Across all columns, **Standardisation of protocols** and **Access to infrastructure** remain consistently strong. Even when not the top item in a given domain, they sit close to the top band, confirming them as systemic levers. The practical implication is that shared SOPs, quality systems, and access mechanisms will benefit *every* domain and reduce fragmentation in multi-institution collaborations. By analysing **Food vs. Environment**, the heatmap makes the two co-leaders of the overall sample visible in domain context. Sustainable/functional packaging glows brightest in the Food column, while Environmental fate & degradation is most intense in Environment and Cross-domain. The proximity of these two needs across columns is clearly explainable considering that innovation in packaging requires environmental evidence, and environmental programmes increasingly evaluate anthropogenic materials and food-pack interfaces. The heatmap therefore supports a programme logic in which method development, Reference Materials, and inter-laboratory

comparisons are co-designed by Food and Environment teams, with Health contributing exposure endpoints and One Health framing. By analysing **Health vs. Cross-domain**, in the Health column the heatmap reinforces the histogram's outcomes related to human exposure modelling, One Health, and access. Crucially, the matrix shows Cross-sectoral data integration appearing at meaningful levels in Cross-domain and Health, signalling the need for template data models, harmonised metadata, and curated reference datasets that can be exploited across studies. This explains why many health stakeholders also call for Traceability/authenticity not just as a food domain task, but as a foundation for connecting upstream measurements to downstream exposure models. The **Cross-domain** column acts as an accelerator for shared enablers: Access, Standardisation, Integration, and One Health all appear at comparatively high shares. This is the category most ready to take advantage of interoperable services - common schemes, shared storage, agreed SOPs - because their workflows inherently cross boundaries. This suggests that cross-domain pilots shall find more immediate users and demonstrable value.

To further explore whether priorities differ depending on the role of respondents within the research and innovation ecosystem, priority needs were also **analysed by stakeholder category**. Figure 5 provides a comparative view of the most frequently selected priority needs across different stakeholder categories. The comparative histogram by stakeholder category provides an additional and highly informative perspective on the prioritisation of research and service needs within the FHERITALE community. While the aggregated results highlight common priorities across the dataset, the stakeholder-based comparison makes it possible to observe how these priorities are distributed differently depending on institutional role, mission and position within the research and innovation ecosystem.

Overall, the comparison confirms a strong convergence across stakeholder categories on a limited number of strategic needs, particularly those related to **environmental fate and degradation, standardisation of protocols, and access to research infrastructures**. These themes consistently appear among the top-ranked priorities across RIs, academic institutions, industry and other stakeholder groups, indicating that they represent shared bottlenecks rather than sector-specific concerns.

RIs tend to assign relatively high importance to environmental fate and degradation and to standardisation-related needs, reflecting their role as service providers and reference centres for validated methodologies. From this perspective, the emphasis on standardisation is closely linked to the need to ensure comparability of data, reproducibility of results and long-term service sustainability across distributed facilities.

Academic institutions show a more diversified pattern of priorities, with strong attention not only to environmental fate and degradation but also to sustainable and functional food packaging and One Health assessment frameworks. This reflects the broader exploratory and hypothesis-driven nature of academic research, where emerging topics and cross-domain integration are often pursued alongside more established analytical needs.

Industry and technology developers display a pronounced focus on access to infrastructure and standardisation of protocols, confirming that barriers related to accessibility, cost, and lack

of harmonised procedures remain critical obstacles for the uptake of advanced analytical and testing services. For these stakeholders, the availability of technically mature tools is not sufficient if access conditions are unclear or if results cannot be easily translated into regulatory or market-relevant evidence.

Civil society and other stakeholder categories, while represented by smaller absolute numbers, also tend to emphasise environmental monitoring and transparency-related needs, such as traceability and authenticity monitoring, highlighting societal expectations around safety, accountability and environmental responsibility.

Taken together, the comparative histogram confirms that differences between stakeholder categories are mainly expressed in the relative weight assigned to priorities, rather than in fundamentally divergent agendas. This convergence reinforces the relevance of addressing a limited set of cross-cutting needs through coordinated service development and targeted investments, rather than fragmented, stakeholder-specific solutions.

Moreover, an heatmap of priority needs by stakeholder category was developed to complement the histogram by offering a more granular view of how individual needs are distributed across different types of organisations (Figure 6). By visualising the share of respondents within each category selecting a given need, the heatmap highlights both areas of strong consensus and domains where perceptions diverge.

A first clear pattern emerging from the heatmap is the high and relatively uniform intensity of selection for **environmental fate and degradation** and **standardisation of protocols** across almost all stakeholder categories. This visual consistency confirms that these needs are widely recognised as foundational requirements for advancing research and service provision in the field of artificial materials.

In contrast, **needs related to human exposure modelling, risk assessment and cross-sectoral data integration** show more heterogeneous patterns, with higher intensity among **academic institutions and Research Infrastructures**, and comparatively lower selection rates among industry-oriented respondents. This suggests that while these topics are considered scientifically important, their translation into applied services may still face challenges related to maturity, validation or regulatory alignment.

Access to infrastructure emerges in the heatmap as a particularly salient issue for industry and technology developers, where high selection intensity reflects practical constraints linked to availability, costs, and procedural complexity. This pattern is less pronounced among Research Infrastructures themselves, underlining the asymmetry between service providers and service users in terms of perceived accessibility.

The heatmap also reveals that **traceability and authenticity monitoring**, while not always among the top-ranked needs in aggregate counts, show concentrated relevance for specific stakeholder groups, notably those closer to **applied food systems and regulatory contexts**. This reinforces the importance of not relying solely on overall rankings, but of considering stakeholder-specific signals when designing future services.

By combining the histogram and heatmap analyses, a coherent picture emerges: priority needs are broadly shared, but the underlying motivations and practical implications differ across

stakeholder categories. This finding supports the WP6 methodological choice to integrate quantitative aggregation with stakeholder-based segmentation and qualitative interpretation, ensuring that the resulting gap analysis captures both convergence and diversity within the FHERITALE community.

Fig.5. Top priority needs by stakeholder category.

The chart compares how the five most frequently selected research needs rank across different stakeholder groups: Research Infrastructures, Academic Institutions, Industry/Technology Developers, Civil Society, and Others. Each cluster on the horizontal axis represents one of the top needs identified in the survey. The bars show the percentage of respondents within each stakeholder category who selected that need. The categories are distinguished by colours.

Fig.6. Heatmap of the priority needs identified according to stakeholder categories.

The heatmap visualises, for each organisation type, the share of respondents who selected a given research need (0–1 scale). Organisation categories are shown on the rows, while columns list the needs ordered by their overall average share. Read row-wise to understand what each stakeholder group prioritises; read column-wise to see which needs are broadly shared across categories versus those that are more specific.

4.2 Technology readiness and Service Readiness Classification

The assessment of technology readiness represents a central element of the WP6 gap analysis, as it provides a structured view of how mature, accessible and operational different analytical, modelling and experimental approaches are perceived to be by the stakeholder community. Within FHERITALE, technology readiness is not understood solely as technical performance, but rather as a composite concept encompassing availability, validation status, usability across domains, and suitability for integration into research services.

The Service Readiness Classification (SRC) framework adopted in this deliverable builds upon the categorisation introduced in WP5 and translates stakeholder perceptions into three main readiness levels:

- A. Fully operational and accessible services
- B. Available but with limitations
- C. Emerging or experimental technologies

complemented by a “Not known” category to explicitly capture uncertainty and knowledge gaps.

An overview of the perceived readiness levels for the set of selected technologies is presented in Figure 7, which illustrates the distribution of readiness classifications across all surveyed technologies, highlighting marked differences between well-established analytical techniques and more innovative or niche approaches.

Overall, techniques such as **FTIR spectroscopy, LC-MS, ICP-MS and RNA-seq** are predominantly classified as **A or B**, reflecting their widespread use, established protocols and relatively broad accessibility across Research Infrastructures and academic laboratories. These technologies are perceived as mature building blocks for service provision, even when applied to complex matrices such as food, environmental or biological samples.

In contrast, **in vivo toxicokinetics, ex vivo placental perfusion assays, PBPK modelling and 3D bioprinted organoids** show a much higher share of **C** and “**Not known**” responses. This pattern does not necessarily reflect a lack of scientific value, but rather points to limited diffusion, higher entry barriers, ethical or regulatory constraints, and uneven availability across institutions and countries.

Importantly, the explicit inclusion of the “**Not known**” category provides valuable information in itself. Rather than being treated as missing data, these responses highlight areas where awareness, training or communication around existing capabilities may be insufficient.

Fig.7. Technology readiness assessment by technology (share of responses, A/B/C/Not known)

To support a more synthetic comparison across technologies, readiness levels were converted into a numerical index (A = 3, B = 2, C = 1), allowing the calculation of an average readiness score for each technology. The resulting ranking is shown in Figure 8.

This representation confirms and sharpens the trends observed in the categorical distribution.

FTIR spectroscopy achieves the highest average readiness score, followed closely by **LC-MS, RNA-seq and ICP-MS**, all of which cluster in the upper part of the readiness spectrum. These

technologies form the current backbone of many analytical services and are widely perceived as reliable, validated and scalable.

Conversely, **ex vivo placental perfusion assays, 3D bioprinted organoids and PBPK modelling** occupy the lower end of the readiness index. Their lower scores reflect not only technical immaturity in some contexts but also limited integration into standard service workflows and a lack of harmonised protocols across domains.

The intermediate positioning of **Electron Microscopy (EM) and advanced image analysis tools** illustrates a transitional status: these technologies are technically advanced and increasingly used, yet still constrained by access to specialised infrastructures, expertise requirements and, in some cases, data interpretation challenges. It is important to note that the category “Not known” does not indicate the absence of a technology, but rather reflects limited awareness, experience or confidence among respondents regarding its maturity and applicability. In this sense, a high share of “Not known” responses can be interpreted as an indicator for knowledge gaps, insufficient dissemination, or lack of exposure to specific methods outside specialised communities.

A complementary perspective on technology readiness is provided by the analysis of “Not known” responses, presented in Figure 9, which highlights substantial differences in stakeholder familiarity across technologies. The highest shares of “Not known” responses are observed for **PBPK modelling, ex vivo placental perfusion assays and 3D bioprinted organoids**, indicating that a significant portion of respondents either lack direct experience with these approaches or are uncertain about their current service-level readiness. This suggests that, beyond technical development, there is a clear need for improved visibility, training and knowledge exchange around these methods. In contrast, classical analytical techniques such as **FTIR, LC-MS and ICP-MS** display comparatively low levels of uncertainty, reinforcing their status as well-understood and widely disseminated tools.

From a service design perspective, these findings are highly relevant: high “Not known” shares point to latent capabilities that may already exist within specific infrastructures but remain underutilised due to limited awareness or unclear access conditions.

Fig.8. Average technology readiness index by technology.

The bar ranks technologies by the mean readiness index (Not known excluded). They represent a compact summary of the A/B/C. Technologies with the highest averages are those with many As and few Cs. Lower averages point to immaturity or uneven familiarity.

Fig.9. Knowledge gaps: share of 'Not known' by technology (%)

The average readiness index provides a synthetic overview of perceived technological maturity, but it should be interpreted in conjunction with the underlying distribution of A, B and C classifications. Similar average values may conceal very different patterns, such as polarised perceptions between expert and non-expert users, or a coexistence of highly mature applications with more experimental or context-specific uses.

Stakeholder perceptions of readiness also vary according to organisational role. This dimension is explored in the heatmap of Figure 10.

Research Infrastructures and academic institutions generally assign higher readiness scores to established analytical technologies, reflecting their direct involvement in operating and maintaining such facilities. At the same time, these groups tend to provide more conservative assessments for emerging technologies, possibly due to their closer familiarity with operational constraints and validation requirements.

Industry and technology developers, where represented, show more selective engagement, with higher readiness perceptions concentrated on technologies directly relevant to applied research and product development. **Civil society** actors and unspecified respondents exhibit larger gaps and higher variability, underlining the importance of tailored communication strategies for different stakeholder groups.

The domain-specific dimension of readiness is illustrated in Figure 11. While many technologies show relatively consistent readiness levels across Food, Health and Environment, notable differences emerge for more complex or integrative approaches. For example, **PBPK modelling and in vivo toxicokinetics** are perceived as more mature within the Health domain than in Food or Environment, reflecting regulatory traditions and historical use. Conversely, analytical techniques such as **FTIR and LC-MS** display strong readiness across all domains, supporting their role as cross-cutting service components.

The **Cross-domain** category highlights both opportunities and challenges: while some technologies achieve high readiness scores, others reveal fragmentation and uneven adoption, reinforcing the need for harmonised approaches under a One Health perspective.

A more stringent view of readiness is provided by focusing exclusively on A-level classifications. The heatmap in Figure 12 shows that only a limited subset of technologies consistently achieves high readiness across stakeholder groups.

Established analytical methods dominate this category, while innovative biological and modelling approaches rarely reach A-level readiness outside specific contexts. This highlights a structural gap between scientific innovation and service-level deployment, which cannot be addressed solely through technological advancement but requires coordinated investment, validation and service integration.

Fig.10. Heatmap of the average technology readiness by organisation category.

The heatmap shows, for each organisation type, the average readiness index assigned to each technology (“Not known” excluded). Organisation categories are listed on the rows; technologies appear on the columns. Darker shades indicate higher average readiness (closer to A). Read row-wise to see which technologies each stakeholder group considers most mature; read column-wise to identify technologies that are broadly rated as ready versus those with lower or uneven scores.

Fig.11. Heatmap of the average technology readiness by organisation category.

The heatmap shows, for each organisation type, the average readiness index assigned to each technology (“Not known” excluded). Organisation categories are listed on the rows; technologies appear on the columns. Darker shades indicate higher average readiness (closer to A). Read row-wise to see which technologies each stakeholder group considers most mature; read column-wise to identify technologies that are broadly rated as ready versus those with lower or uneven scores.

Fig.12. Heatmap of the average technology readiness by domain.

The heatmap shows, for each domain (Food, Health, Environment, Cross-domain), the average readiness index assigned to each technology (“Not known” excluded). Domains are listed on the rows, while technologies appear on the columns with shortened, wrapped labels for clarity. Darker shades indicate higher average readiness (closer to A). Read row-wise to see which technologies each domain considers most mature; read column-wise to identify technologies that are broadly rated as ready versus those with lower or uneven scores.

The aggregated distribution of readiness classifications across all technologies is presented in the heatmap of Figure 13, where the predominance of “Not known” responses at the aggregate level is a striking result, indicating that uncertainty and partial knowledge remain widespread even among expert stakeholders. This finding reinforces the conclusion that gaps are not limited to missing technologies, but also include limited transparency, fragmented information and limited or unequal access to existing services.

Fig.13. Overall distribution of readiness classifications (all technologies)

In addition to technology readiness, the perception of the feasibility to address priority needs using existing technologies and services, on a scale from 1 to 5 was also assessed. In fact, while SRC classifications capture perceived technological maturity, they do not fully account for organisational, regulatory and operational factors that condition the actual usability of technologies as services.

The overall results are shown in Figure 14. Highest feasibility scores are associated with access to infrastructures, improved cross-domain collaboration and development of new methods, suggesting that stakeholders perceive these needs as addressable in the short to medium term if organisational and coordination barriers are reduced. Lower scores for regulatory clarity and data harmonisation tools point to structural challenges that extend beyond individual services. The organisational and domain-specific breakdown of feasibility perceptions is illustrated in Figures 15 and 16. These heatmaps reveal systematic differences in expectations: industry stakeholders tend to express higher feasibility for practical improvements, while academic and RI respondents adopt a more cautious stance, reflecting operational realities (Fig. 15).

Across domains, feasibility is generally perceived as higher in the Cross-domain and Environment contexts, whereas Health shows greater sensitivity to regulatory and ethical constraints (Fig. 16).

The final analysis step focuses on user-defined criteria for service usefulness, providing a direct link between technological and organisational readiness and expectations regarding future service development. As shown in Figure 17, respondents clearly prioritise **support and training**, **ease of access**, and **cost-effectiveness** as the most important features of a new service. These aspects resulted in consistently more important than purely technical attributes, such as interoperability or regulatory relevance, highlighting that even mature technologies may fail to generate impact if not embedded within accessible, well-supported and economically viable service models. The prominence of **validated protocols** further confirms the importance of trust, reliability and standardisation, particularly in cross-domain contexts where results must be comparable and defensible across regulatory, scientific and industrial settings. Overall, these results reinforce the need for a user-centred approach to service design within FHERITALE, where technological excellence is complemented by training, guidance and clear access pathways, ensuring that services are not only available, but effectively usable by a wide and diverse community.

Fig.14. Service readiness: feasibility of addressing needs with existing technologies/services (average, feasibility ratings 1-5)

Fig.15. Heatmap of the feasibility (service readiness) by organisation category.

The heatmap shows, for each organisation type, the average feasibility score for addressing each need with existing technologies/services (1–5 scale). Organisation categories are listed on the rows, while columns list the needs. Darker shades indicate higher average feasibility (closer to 5). Read row-wise to see which needs each stakeholder group considers more service-ready; read column-wise to identify needs that are broadly feasible across categories versus those with lower or uneven scores. (Averages exclude non-responses; “Unspecified” reflects missing organisation data.).

Fig.16. Heatmap of the feasibility (service readiness) by domain.

The heatmap shows, for each domain, the average feasibility score for addressing each need with existing technologies/services (1–5 scale). Domains are listed on the rows, while columns list the needs. Darker shades indicate higher average feasibility (closer to 5). Read row-wise to see which needs each domain considers more service-ready; read column-wise to identify needs that are broadly feasible across domains versus those with lower or uneven scores.

Fig.17. Perspective on what makes a new service useful

4.3 Identified gaps and barriers

A central objective of WP6 is to move beyond a simple inventory of “what exists” and to describe, in a realistic way, what prevents existing capabilities from being used as effective and scalable services. In the context of artificial materials, where methods, matrices, exposure pathways and regulatory expectations evolve rapidly, respondents did not describe gaps only as missing instruments or missing expertise. Instead, the survey and the outcomes of the Bucharest workshop show a more layered picture: services may exist, but still fail to function as accessible and reliable “building blocks” for cross-domain research and decision-making. The gap analysis therefore distinguishes between different types of shortcomings (e.g., access, validation, interoperability) and complements them with concrete barriers that affect service uptake (e.g., costs, complexity).

The overall distribution of reported gap types highlights a strong concentration around **access, knowledge and interoperability**, with validation gaps also present at a meaningful level, while regulatory gaps appear less frequently in the dataset, even though still relevant in specific contexts). This pattern is shown in Figure 18, which reports the share of respondents selecting each gap type. Access gaps are the most frequently reported category overall, followed closely by knowledge and interoperability gaps. This distribution suggests that the most common problems are not necessarily linked to the “absence” of technologies, but to the **conditions required for those technologies to become usable and accessible services**. For example, access gaps typically reflect limitations such as restricted availability of advanced facilities, limited capacity for external users, long waiting times, uneven geographic distribution of infrastructures, and administrative obstacles. Knowledge gaps, by contrast, relate to the lack of practical guidance, shared protocols, or training pathways that enable users to apply methods correctly and interpret results confidently, especially when they are related to complex matrices or when results are close to detection limits. Therefore, in this sense metrological support can cover a strategic role. Interoperability gaps stand out as particularly important, because they cut across domains and stakeholder roles. Interoperability frequently resulted not only as a “data issue”, but as a broader service-level challenge: differences in metadata, reporting formats, sample descriptors, QA/QC approaches, and terminologies prevent efficient comparison and aggregation of results. This is a critical barrier in One Health-oriented research, where evidence must be combined across food, biological systems and the environment.

Fig.18. Overall distribution of gap types (%)

While the overall distribution provides a useful baseline, it is equally important to understand whether different stakeholder categories experience gaps in different ways. The consultations confirm that **stakeholder roles shape how gaps are perceived and reported**, which is expected in a service ecosystem where some actors mainly provide services (e.g., RIs), while others are primarily users or intermediaries (e.g., academia, industry-facing stakeholders, and public bodies).

A comparative view is presented in Figure 19, showing how often each stakeholder category indicated each gap type. It makes visible the “profile” of gaps across communities: some categories are more likely to emphasise barriers related to service accessibility and operational constraints, while others may focus on knowledge and validation aspects, often reflecting differences in internal capacity, regulatory pressures, and proximity to end-user needs. “Higher” indications can reflect both (i) genuine higher exposure to a barrier, and (ii) a stronger awareness of that barrier due to professional experience. In particular, “knowledge gaps” can be reported at higher rates by groups that are actively trying to implement methods and therefore encounter practical limitations first-hand. Importantly, these differences should not be read as contradictions. Instead, they reflect the fact that a service ecosystem succeeds only when it aligns multiple layers at once: technical capability, service accessibility, quality and validation, and interoperable outputs. If one layer fails, users experience the entire chain as fragile.

Fig.19. Gaps by stakeholder category (%)

In addition to stakeholder differences, the survey also makes it possible to explore gaps through a domain lens. This is especially relevant for FHERITALE because the project explicitly operates at the Food-Health-Environment interface: services must be able to support research questions that move across compartments and use comparable approaches.

The heatmap in Figure 20 presents the distribution of gap types by domain, helping to identify which issues are “universal” and which are more domain-specific. For instance:

- **Access gaps** can manifest differently depending on domain: in some cases, they reflect limited access to advanced instrumentation and trained staff; in others they reflect limited access to biological models, ethical approvals, or specialised facilities.
- **Validation gaps** may be more prominent where methods are still evolving rapidly or where (Certified) Reference Materials and inter-laboratory comparisons are less available or mature.
- **Interoperability gaps** are expected to remain high across domains because they become most visible exactly when cross-domain integration is attempted (e.g., linking exposure data from environmental samples to biological response data).

Therefore, it can be stressed that there is no “single domain solution”: even when gap types look similar at a first glance, the underlying causes may differ. This reinforces the importance of service design that is domain-aware but still aligned with shared, cross-domain standards.

Fig.20. Heatmap of gaps by domain.

Heatmap showing, for each domain (Food, Health, Environment, Cross-domain), the percentage of respondents who indicated each gap type. Darker shades correspond to higher shares. Read row-wise to understand domain-specific priorities; read column-wise to identify gaps that cut across domains

Alongside gap types, consultations covered the indication of concrete barriers that hinder uptake of services. This framing is important because it connects gap analysis to operational reality: even a technically mature method can fail as a service if users cannot access it, afford it, understand how to use it, or obtain outputs that are comparable and reusable.

The overall distribution of barriers is shown in Figure 21. In the dataset, cost emerges as the most frequently reported barrier, followed by a group of secondary barriers that still matter in practice (support availability, location, complexity, and lack of protocols). This result is consistent with a service ecosystem where many needs require expensive instrumentation, specialised staff time, and careful quality assurance. However, cost should be interpreted broadly, meaning the full cost of making an activity feasible, including – as an example – sample preparation and logistics, time to access a facility, staff training, data processing and reporting, and the risk that an experiment fails or results are not accepted by peers or regulators due to missing validation.

The presence of “complexity” and “support” as barriers also indicates that users value services that streamline the process (service provision): services are more likely to be used when they come with clear onboarding, guidance, and troubleshooting, especially for advanced methods and cross-domain workflows. Finally, “lack of protocols” remains a barrier even when it appears as a smaller percentage: it is often a multiplier effect barrier, because missing protocols amplify complexity, reduce comparability and reliability, and increase costs indirectly.

Fig.21. Barriers to service uptake

Taken together, the gap and barrier results suggest that the service ecosystem required by FHERITALE is constrained by a combination of **structural limitations (access and cost)** and **system-level enablers (knowledge, validation, interoperability)**. This suggests that service development should not focus only on adding “new techniques”, but also on strengthening the conditions that allow techniques to function as reliable services across Europe.

In practical terms, the survey results point towards a set of priorities that will likely deliver high impact across domains:

- **Improving access pathways** (clear entry points, transparent conditions, reduced administrative difficulties, shared booking and support models)
- **Strengthening knowledge transfer** (training, user support, practical guidance, exemplars, and peer learning)
- **Embedding validation mechanisms** (e.g., inter-laboratory exercises, QA/QC packages, reference materials and reporting conventions)
- **Delivering interoperability by design** (e.g., shared metadata, harmonised reporting templates, and data integration tools that respect domain-specific constraints).

4.4 Cross-domain patterns and synthesis

The analysis carried out in Task 6.1 clearly highlights that **the main challenge is not the absence of technology in absolute terms, but the different level of/not sufficient maturity, access and integration of technologies across domains and stakeholder communities**. Looking at the dataset as a whole, shared needs emerge, while important domain- and organisation-specific differences explain why some services are perceived as established and operational in one context, and still experimental or difficult to use in another.

A first cross-domain trend is the **recurrence of a small set of priorities that are simultaneously scientific and organisational**. Across Food, Health, Environment and cross-domain responses, participants repeatedly pointed out the need for harmonised protocols, better

access to infrastructures, and data interoperability as conditions that enable almost every other objective. Therefore, these priorities are not related to a single discipline, but they represent enabling factors that cut across analytical chemistry, exposure science, toxicology, environmental monitoring, and digital infrastructures. It also underlines the need to produce results that are comparable, reusable and easier to translate between laboratories, sectors and countries.

A second recurring theme concerns the relationship between **technological maturity** and **practical usability**. The Service Readiness Classification (SRC) results show that several analytical platforms are perceived as relatively mature, but this maturity is not automatically converted into service uptake. Therefore, having the instrument/tool does not directly correspond to having an accessible, validated and well-supported service. The readiness assessment by technology, together with the average readiness and the overall distribution of classifications, shows that perceived maturity is often accompanied by a substantial share of “Not known” responses for the same technology category, indicating that visibility and familiarity vary significantly even within a well-informed respondent pool. This knowledge gap highlights an additional barrier: some capabilities exist, but they are not clearly reflected, not widely shared, or not arranged in a way that makes them discoverable and usable by non-specialist users.

A third cross-domain pattern is the **consistent prominence of “Not known” as a signal**, rather than a residual category. Where “Not known” is high, it more often indicates that services are either: i) emerging, ii) limited to a small expert community, or, iii) too context-dependent to be assessed confidently by a broader audience. From a service design perspective, it suggests that the pathway to maturity may require not only technical development but also community building, training, and clearer service definitions (what the service is, what it delivers, and under which assumptions it is valid).

A fourth important topic is the **tight coupling between gaps and barriers**. When respondents describe gaps, they are frequently describing the same constraints from different angles. For instance, an “access gap” is often linked to cost, limited availability, long waiting times, or geographic concentration of facilities; an “interoperability gap” is frequently linked to heterogeneity of data formats and incomplete metadata; and a “validation gap” often aligns with the lack of shared protocols, inter-laboratory exercises, or agreed performance criteria. The overall distribution of gap types, the breakdown by stakeholder category, and the gap patterns by domain suggest that no single barrier dominates in isolation, while barriers cluster and reinforce each other. This implies that solving one issue (e.g., opening access to a facility) may not deliver the expected benefits if other enabling conditions (e.g., harmonised workflows, training, data pipelines) are not addressed at the same time.

A fifth and particularly strategic trend relates to **stakeholder segmentation**, which helps interpret why priorities look “shared” at the top level but diverge in practice. The conceptual synthesis presented in Figure 22 depicts a compact view of these differences: RIs and academia tend to emphasise protocol harmonisation, access and the integration of analytical with digital workflows, while regulatory-facing actors give higher importance to reliability, traceability,

and validation pathways that can support evidence-based assessment. Industry and technology developers often converge on the need for practical, cost-aware services with predictable turnaround times and clearer service-level expectations. EU projects and public bodies, finally, tend to surface system-level concerns: fragmentation of data ecosystems, duplicated efforts, and the difficulty of coordinating cross-domain work without shared digital and governance frameworks. These outcomes show that stakeholder differences are not conflicting, but mainly represent **different stages along the same chain**. As an example, a regulator asking for validation and comparability is often dependent on the same elements that researchers ask for (shared protocols, data reliability, access to infrastructures). Similarly, industry’s focus on cost and ease of access often reflects real constraints that also affect academic research, particularly where advanced facilities are limited or when the demand exceeds the capacity. In this sense, segmentation clarifies where targeted interventions could unlock broader benefits for the whole community.

Fig.22. Stakeholder segmentation: specific priorities and perspectives

Finally, the cross-domain analysis points to a practical interpretation of “service readiness” that goes beyond the SRC label alone. The user perspective on what makes a service useful indicates that **support/training, ease of access, cost-effectiveness and validated protocols** are decisive. This is consistent with the observation that technologies may be known and even available but still perceived as difficult to use in routine research or applied contexts. Taken together, these findings suggest that a future service ecosystem should be designed not only around instruments, methods and tools, but also around **how users enter the system**, how they are supported, how results are made comparable, and how data outputs become reusable across domains.

Overall, the cross-domain patterns emerging from the entire analysis result coherent: **maturity, access, validation and interoperability represent the pillars determining whether**

technologies can become functioning services. When these pillars are aligned, stakeholders experience the service landscape as enabling; when they are misaligned, even technically mature tools may remain underused or trusted only within narrow expert communities.

5. Implications for clustering and future actions

The analysis presented in the previous sections highlights a clear need to move beyond a technology-by-technology or domain-by-domain perspective. Stakeholder inputs consistently point to the importance of **integrated service solutions**, capable of addressing complex research and regulatory questions related to artificial materials across food, health and environmental contexts.

Rather than identifying isolated gaps, the results underline the presence of **shared needs and recurring bottlenecks** that cut across domains, technologies and stakeholder categories. This provides a strong rationale for the development of **service clusters**, understood as coordinated sets of infrastructures, tools, expertise and support functions that can jointly respond to these needs.

Survey and workshop results show that many technologies are already available at a reasonable level of maturity, particularly in the area of analytical and characterisation techniques (e.g. spectroscopy, chromatography and mass spectrometry). These technologies are widely used and, in many cases, well established within RIs and specialised laboratories. However, stakeholders repeatedly stressed that **the real added value does not lie in individual tools**, but in the way these tools are combined into **end-to-end services**. For example, high interest in environmental fate and degradation, sustainable packaging, and One Health assessment does not translate into demand for single measurements or standalone experiments. Instead, users are looking for **integrated workflows** that link analytical data, exposure models, biological testing and interpretation frameworks. This includes not only technical integration, but also coordinated access, shared protocols, and clear guidance on how different methods should be combined and interpreted.

This shift from technologies to services is clearly reflected in the Service Readiness Classification results (see Section 4.2), where some technologies appear mature in isolation, but less ready when considered as part of a complete service offering. As illustrated in Figure 23, areas such as analytical characterisation or environmental monitoring show relatively high readiness at the technology level, while services involving biological models or complex exposure modelling remain at lower readiness due to validation, standardisation and integration gaps.

Service Area	Examples / Tools	Readiness (SRC)
Environmental monitoring	Detection of MNPs, fate & degradation	B–A
Analytical & characterization services	FTIR, LC-MS, ICP-MS	A–B
Toxicology & exposure modeling	In vivo / PBPK / One Health	B–C
Biological models	3D organoids, ex vivo assays	C
Data interoperability & digital tools	Image analysis, data integration	B
Sustainable packaging & materials	Eco-functional packaging R&D	B–A

Fig.23. Stakeholder segmentation: specific priorities and perspectives

Clustering therefore becomes a practical way to bridge this gap, by connecting existing capacities and filling missing links through coordination rather than duplication. By grouping complementary technologies into coherent service-oriented clusters, it becomes possible to move from fragmented capabilities to structured service portfolios that better respond to user needs, reduce access barriers and support cross-domain applications. In this sense, clustering is not only a technical exercise, but also an organisational and strategic tool to maximise the impact of existing investments.

Based on the convergence of survey results, workshop discussions and open-text responses, several preliminary **priority clustering areas** clearly emerge. These proposed preliminary clusters reflect both the needs expressed by stakeholders and the current level of maturity and availability of technologies and services. An overview of the proposed clusters and their main characteristics is illustrated in Figure 24.

Environmental monitoring	Analytical & characterisation services	Toxicology & Exposure modelling	Biological models & In-vitro systems	Data interoperability & Digital tools	Sustainable packaging & Functional materials
<p>Scope: Detection of MNPs, fate & degradation, environmental impact</p> <p>Technologies: FTIR, LC-MS, imaging tools</p> <p>Readiness (SRC): B–A</p> <p>Users: RIs, regulatory agencies, EU projects</p>	<p>Scope: Chemical analysis, spectrometry, material characterisation</p> <p>Technologies: LC-MS, FTIR, ICP-MS</p> <p>Readiness (SRC): A–B</p> <p>Users: Industry, RIs, regulators</p>	<p>Scope: PBPK, in vivo/in vitro, One Health assessment</p> <p>Technologies: PBPK modelling, in vivo tox, omics integration</p> <p>Readiness (SRC): B–C</p> <p>Users: Academia, regulators, RIs</p>	<p>Scope: Organoids, ex vivo assays, 3D systems</p> <p>Technologies: 3D organoids, placental perfusion, ex vivo platforms</p> <p>Readiness (SRC): C</p> <p>Users: Research groups, RIs, EU consortia</p>	<p>Scope: Image analysis, data integration, FAIR pipelines</p> <p>Technologies: Digital analysis, AI tools, interoperable platforms</p> <p>Readiness (SRC): B</p> <p>Users: All stakeholder groups</p>	<p>Scope: Eco-functional materials, circularity, functional properties</p> <p>Technologies: Material testing, chemical profiling</p> <p>Readiness (SRC): B–A</p> <p>Users: Industry, academia, RIs</p>

Fig.24. Cluster suggestion. Readiness ranges reflect the diversity of perceptions across stakeholder groups and application contexts

A first cluster concerns **environmental monitoring and impact assessment**, bringing together detection of micro- and nanoplastics, fate and degradation studies, and environmental exposure modelling. This cluster responds to strong demand from both research and policy-oriented stakeholders and aligns with existing analytical capacities that can be further strengthened through harmonisation and shared protocols.

A second cluster relates to **analytical and characterisation services**, which form the backbone of many other activities. While these technologies often show high readiness, stakeholders identified recurring issues related to access, costs and comparability of results. Clustering these services around shared access schemes and standard operating procedures would significantly increase their usability.

A third cluster focuses on **toxicology and exposure modelling**, including in vitro, in vivo and in silico approaches. Here, readiness levels vary substantially across different methods and applications, with some tools already in use and others still at an earlier stage of development. However, the demand is strong, and stakeholder interest is consistently high particularly for approaches that link exposure, hazard and risk assessment across environmental and human health contexts. Coordinated clustering can help concentrate expertise, support validation efforts and facilitate the gradual transition of emerging tools towards operational use.

Further clusters emerge around **data interoperability and digital tools**, as well as **sustainable packaging and functional materials**. In both cases, stakeholders emphasised the need for services that go beyond data generation, offering support for data integration, interpretation, and practical application in regulatory or industrial contexts.

Clustering is not an end in itself, but a means to address the main gaps identified (see Section 4.3). In particular, **access gaps** and **interoperability gaps** appear well suited to be tackled through coordinated service structures.

Limited access to advanced infrastructures, long waiting times and differences in geographical availability were frequently mentioned by respondents. Clusters can mitigate these issues by enabling **shared access models**, clearer service catalogues and transparent conditions for use. Similarly, lack of harmonised methods and fragmented data practices were identified as major obstacles. Within a cluster, common protocols, reference datasets and agreed data standards can be developed and maintained more effectively than through isolated initiatives.

Importantly, clustering also offers a framework to address **skills and capacity gaps**. Several stakeholders highlighted the need for training, guidance and user support. Embedding these elements directly into service clusters, rather than treating them as separate activities, can significantly improve service uptake and long-term impact.

The findings of Task 6.1 reported in this deliverable provide a solid evidence base to inform subsequent activities within FHERITALE and beyond. The clustering logic emerging from the analysis directly supports the transition towards Task 6.2, where service concepts can be further refined, tested and aligned with stakeholder expectations. Moreover, the evidence and priorities identified also provide a structured input to Deliverable D5.2 - *Strategic technology and service needs*, supporting the identification of priority areas for investment, coordination and long-term service development

More broadly, the results suggest that future actions should prioritise:

- **Coordination over expansion**, focusing on better use of existing capacities rather than creating new, isolated services
- **Validation and harmonisation**, particularly for emerging technologies that show high potential but limited readiness
- **User-oriented service design**, ensuring that access conditions, support and documentation are integral parts of service offers
- **Cross-domain integration**, reflecting the interconnected nature of food, health and environmental challenges.

By grounding clustering strategies in real stakeholder needs and documented gaps, the project can ensure that future services are not only technically sound, but also **relevant, usable and sustainable** in the long term.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable D6.1 provides a comprehensive and evidence-based overview of the main gaps and emerging technology needs related to artificial materials across food systems, human health and the environment. The analysis builds directly on the technological mapping and readiness assessment developed in WP5, as documented in Deliverable D5.1 and Milestones MS6 and MS7, and extends it through a stakeholder-driven gap analysis and prioritisation exercise. By combining structured data collection with qualitative dialogue and iterative validation, Task 6.1 has made it possible to move beyond a purely descriptive mapping of existing capabilities and to capture how services are actually perceived, accessed and used by different stakeholder communities.

One of the most relevant outcomes of the gap analysis is the clear convergence around a limited number of cross-cutting priorities. Environmental fate and degradation, access to research infrastructures, standardisation of protocols, and One Health-oriented approaches consistently emerge as central needs across domains and stakeholder categories. This convergence suggests that the most pressing challenges are not confined to a single sector or discipline, but reflect systemic conditions that affect the entire research and innovation ecosystem dealing with artificial materials.

At the same time, the analysis highlights that the existence of technologies alone is not sufficient to guarantee effective service provision. Many technologies are perceived as technically mature, but still remain difficult to use in practice due to access constraints, limited validation, fragmented knowledge, or lack of interoperability. The Service Readiness Classification has proven particularly useful in revealing this distinction between technological maturity and service usability, showing that readiness is shaped as much by organisational and contextual factors as by technical performance.

The identification of gaps and barriers further reinforces this perspective. Respondents rarely pointed to the complete absence of technologies as the main problem. Instead, they emphasised barriers related to access, costs, knowledge transfer, validation and data integration. These findings underline that future efforts should prioritise the conditions that allow existing capabilities to function as reliable, accessible and trusted services, rather than focusing exclusively on the development of new tools.

A key added value of WP6 lies in its co-creation-driven approach. The combination of an online Focus Group, a large-scale survey and an in-person workshop allowed for continuous validation and refinement of results, ensuring that the analysis reflects lived research and operational practice. The Bucharest workshop, in particular, played a crucial role in transforming individual survey responses into shared interpretations and in linking gap analysis outcomes to future-oriented actions. This process helped distinguish widely shared priorities from more context-specific concerns and provided a realistic assessment of feasibility.

Importantly, the results of Task 6.1 establish a clear bridge towards the next phases of the project. The identified needs, readiness levels and barriers provide a concrete basis for the definition of thematic clusters of services and actors under Task 6.2. Rather than proposing clusters based on technologies alone, the evidence supports a service-oriented logic, where analytical tools, modelling approaches and support functions are combined into integrated workflows aligned with user expectations.

Beyond WP6, the outcomes of this deliverable directly inform the coordination and development of services in WP7 and the strategic planning and sustainability activities of WP8. By grounding these future actions in documented stakeholder needs and validated gaps, FHERITALE is well positioned to design services that are not only technically sound, but also accessible, usable and relevant across domains.

In conclusion, D6.1 represents a key step in shifting from a fragmented landscape of capabilities towards a more coherent and user-driven service ecosystem. By highlighting where alignment is already strong and where targeted effort is still required, this deliverable provides a solid foundation for coordinated action, shared investment and long-term integration of RIs addressing artificial materials in the Food-Health-Environment nexus.

Annex I – Focus Group

Figure I-1 reports the full agenda of the Focus Group. The session was organised around four thematic blocks:

1. **Domains and priority needs**, covering Food, Health, Environment and cross-domain issues
2. **Technology readiness and SRC classification**, focusing on the clarity and applicability of the A/B/C readiness scale
3. **Types of gaps and systemic barriers**, including access, validation, maturity, interoperability and regulatory constraints
4. **Questionnaire review**, with targeted discussion of key survey questions.

Participants were invited to contribute through digital sticky notes, comments and voting mechanisms, allowing both structured feedback and open-ended suggestions. This format facilitated active participation and ensured that divergent views were explicitly captured rather than averaged out. Prior to the session, participants were provided with a preliminary Gap Analysis Matrix and a draft version of the semi-structured questionnaire. These materials were used as working documents during the discussion, allowing participants to comment directly on the proposed domains, gap categories, technology lists and readiness definitions. This preparatory step facilitated a more focused and informed discussion, enabling participants to move beyond abstract considerations and engage with concrete analytical tools. This approach transformed the Focus Group from a purely consultative exercise into an active methodological co-design process, in which participants directly contributed to shaping both the analytical dimensions of the gap analysis and the operational structure of the survey instrument.

Figure I-2 shows a screenshot of the online Focus Group session, while Figure I-3 depicts the whiteboard illustrating the structured layout adopted for validating domains, technologies and gap categories.

Figure II-4 illustrates the stakeholder composition of the Focus Group by stakeholder category, highlighting the diversity of perspectives involved in the validation process.

Focus group
30th of June, 2025, 09⁴⁵ a.m. CET

Link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86359736990>

Agenda

09⁴⁵ – 10⁰⁰	Connecting to Zoom
10⁰⁰ – 10¹⁵	Tour de table
10¹⁵ – 10²⁵	Introduction and objectives
10²⁵ – 10⁴⁰	Domains and priority needs
10⁴⁰ – 10⁵⁵	Technology readiness (SRC)
10⁵⁵ – 11¹⁵	Gaps and barriers
11¹⁵ – 11⁴⁵	Questionnaire review (key questions)
11⁴⁵ – 12¹⁵	Open discussion, wrap-up & reflection

Fig.I-1. Online Focus Group session, 30 June 2025 - Agenda

Fig.I-2. Online Focus Group session, 30 June 2025 - screenshot

Fig.I-3. Example of whiteboards used during the Focus Group (screenshots)

Fig.I-4. Stakeholder composition of the Focus Group

Annex II – On-line questionnaire

In terms of structure, the survey included a total of 41 questions organised into 5 thematic sections progressing from general contextual information to more specific technical and strategic questions. Introductory sections captured the respondent’s profile, institutional background and domain of activity, enabling subsequent segmentation of responses by stakeholder category. Core sections focused on: i) priority needs, ii) technology and service landscape, iii) service gaps and classification. The concluding sections provided space for open reflections, lessons learned from previous experiences, and forward-looking suggestions.

The full text of the questionnaire as exported by LimeSurvey is reported hereinafter.

FHERITALE Gap Analysis Questionnaire – Identifying Needs, Technologies and Service Gaps Across Domains

Questions marked with an asterisk (*) are mandatory

Welcome, and thank you for participating in the FHERITALE (<https://fheritale.eu/home>) stakeholder consultation. The main goal of the project is to provide an overview of the services available to researchers interested in studying the effects on health, nutrition, and the environment of artificial materials at the micro- and nano-scale (especially, but not exclusively, plastics). This questionnaire is part of our ongoing effort to identify priority research needs, service gaps, and critical technologies which are expected to span multiple scales and disciplines, including high-quality metrology, structural biology, microbiology, and ecotoxicology. Your input will directly support the development of thematic maps of services accessible to all European researchers. The survey is semi-structured and designed to take approximately 30 minutes to complete. Your responses are highly valued and will remain confidential. There are 41 questions in this survey.

Respondent Profile

Name & Surname *

e-mail address

Please write your answer here:

only if you agree to be contacted

Gender

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

Age range

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Under 30
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- 60+

Please indicate your domain of expertise *

● Check all that apply
Please choose **all** that apply:

- Food
- Health
- Environment
- Cross-domain

Other:

Possibility of multiple selection

What type of organization do you represent? *

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Research Infrastructure
- Academic institution
- Industry / Technology Developer
- Policy body / Regulator
- NGO
- Civil society
- Other

Which country is your organization based in? *

Please write your answer here:

What is your role in the organization? *

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Scientific / Technical staff
- Management / Coordination
- Policy / Strategy
- Operational / User support
- Other

Are you actively involved in a Research Infrastructure initiative? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

Please indicate the RI(s) you are affiliated with (if any)

Please write your answer here:

Priority Needs

Please select the priority research needs relevant to your work *

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Detection of MNPs in food
 Human exposure modeling
 Environmental fate and degradation
 Traceability and authenticity monitoring
 Sustainable and functional food packaging
 One Health assessment
 Standardization of protocols
 Access to infrastructure
 Cross-sectoral data integration
 Risk assessment

Other:

Possibility of multiple selection

Which food matrices are relevant to your work or expertise?

🗨️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Fruits and vegetables
- Cereals and grain-based products
- Meat and meat products
- Dairy products
- Seafood and fish
- Ready-to-eat or processed foods
- Packaged foods (general)
- Beverages

Other:

Possibility of multiple selection

For the food matrices you selected above, please describe any specific priority needs

Please write your answer here:

You may structure your answer as a list (one per matrix) or as a short paragraph

Have you already tried to address any of the selected priority needs through existing services or infrastructures?

📌 Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes (please explain)
- No
- Not Applicable

Make a comment on your choice here:

Which type of support would most help address these priority needs in your domain? *

📌 Check all that apply
Please choose **all** that apply:

- Access to infrastructures
- Development of new methods
- Improved cross-domain collaboration
- Regulatory clarity
- Data harmonization tools

Other:

Possibility of multiple selection

Please rank the importance of each selected need *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	1	2	3	4	5
Access to infrastructures	<input type="radio"/>				
Development of new methods	<input type="radio"/>				
Improved cross-domain collaboration	<input type="radio"/>				
Regulatory clarity	<input type="radio"/>				
Data harmonization tools	<input type="radio"/>				

1 = low, 5 = critical; please rate the relevance of each need you selected in the previous question

How feasible do you consider addressing these needs with existing technologies/services? *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	1	2	3	4	5
Access to infrastructures	<input type="radio"/>				
Development of new methods	<input type="radio"/>				
Improved cross-domain collaboration	<input type="radio"/>				
Regulatory clarity	<input type="radio"/>				
Data harmonization tools	<input type="radio"/>				

1 = not feasible, 5 = fully feasible

Are there urgent needs under-addressed by current infrastructures

Please write your answer here:

Which sectors are most affected by these unmet needs? *

🗖️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

Academic research

Industry

Public policy

Environment

Other:

Possibility of multiple selection

Are you aware of initiatives addressing these needs? *

🗖️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes (please specify)

No

Make a comment on your choice here:

Which sectors are most affected by these unmet needs? *

🗳️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

Academic research

Industry

Public policy

Environment

Other:

Possibility of multiple selection

Are you aware of initiatives addressing these needs? *

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes (please specify)

No

Make a comment on your choice here:

What criteria should guide the prioritization of future services

Please write your answer here:

Do you have any additional comment?

Please write your answer here:

Technology and Service Landscape

Which of the following technologies do you use or access?

*

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	In use	Not accessible	Not known
FTIR (Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Raman Spectroscopy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ATR-FTIR (Attenuated Total Reflectance)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma MS)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
GC-MS (Gas Chromatography-MS)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Py-GC-MS (Pyrolysis-GC-MS)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
LC-MS (Liquid Chromatography-MS)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Confocal Raman Microspectroscopy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
UV-Visible Spectroscopy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cryo-TEM (Cryogenic Transmission Electron Microscopy)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy (CLSM)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	In use	Not accessible	Not known
Fluorescence Microscopy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
STORM / Super-Resolution Microscopy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Intravital Microscopy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
FTIR Microscopy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
RNA-seq / Transcriptomics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
LC-MS-based Proteomics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
NMR-based Metabolomics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
qPCR / RT-qPCR	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Metagenomics / Microbiomics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Multi-omics integration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Epigenomic profiling	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lipidomics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
PBPK Modeling (Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetics)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In vivo Toxicokinetics (animal models)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3D Bioprinted Organoids	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	In use	Not accessible	Not known
Cell culture assays (e.g. immune, intestinal)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cytotoxicity assays (e.g. CCK-8, LDH)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ROS measurement assays	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gut microbiome analysis	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ex vivo placental perfusion assay	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
FITC-Dextran permeability assay	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ELISA / Immunoassays	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flow Cytometry	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ImageJ / FIJI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
PBPK or QSPR modeling tools	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI tools for screening and prediction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Spectral data processing software (e.g. MassLynx, GROMACS, R, Python)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
FAIR-compliant data repositories	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Particle tracking software (e.g. ParticleScout)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	In use	Not accessible	Not known
Statistical packages (SPSS, R, Python)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Are there any additional technologies you consider critical but not covered in this questionnaire

Please write your answer here:

Which services (linked to the technologies above or others) do you consider critical but currently not accessible to you?

Please write your answer here:

Please describe the type of service and, if possible, the related technology or use case

What are the main barriers to accessing these technologies/services?

🗖️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Cost
- Support
- Location
- Lack of protocols
- Complexity

Other:

Possibility of multiple selection

Are there services that exist but are not aligned to your needs? *

🗖️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes (please explain)
- No
- Not Applicable

Make a comment on your choice here:

Are you developing or adapting any emerging technologies? *

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Not Applicable

Make a comment on your choice here:

Would you test new services in pilot studies? *

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- Not Applicable

What would improve your access or adoption of these technologies?

Please write your answer here:

Do you have any additional comment?

Please write your answer here:

Service Gaps and Classification

Please assess the readiness of the following technologies *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	A	B	C	Not known
FTIR spectroscopy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cryo-TEM	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
PBPK modeling	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3D Bioprinted organoids	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
LC-MS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
RNA-seq	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ICP-MS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ex vivo placental perfusion assay	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In vivo toxicokinetics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Image analysis (ParticleScout / ImageJ)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

A = Fully Operational Services/Technologies; B = Existing but Partially Aligned or Restricted Services/Technologies; C = Technologies Not Ready for Service.
(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15554665>)

For technologies classified as 'B', what improvement is needed? *

! Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Protocols
- Validation
- Access
- Training
- Domain adaptation
- Integration
- Not known

Other:

B = Existing but Partially Aligned or Restricted Services/Technologies; Possibility of multiple selection

For technologies classified as 'C', would you support early-stage development? *

! Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes - collaboration
- Yes - pilot site
- No
- Not known

C = Existing but Partially Aligned or Restricted Services/Technologies

Which actions should be prioritized to close critical gaps? *

🗨️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

Documentation

RI integration

R & D

Access points

Other:

Possibility of multiple selection

Would you contribute to co-designing future RI services? *

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

Maybe

Do you have any additional comment?

Please write your answer here:

Final Inputs

Do you have any additional comment about emerging needs or gaps?

Please write your answer here:

Would you like to share a concrete example – even brief - of a successful or failed service implementation in your field?

Please write your answer here:

Even short stories can help improve future service design and your input can really help identify what works (and what doesn't) in real-life settings

In your opinion, what would make a new service 'useful' from a practical user perspective? *

! Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Easy access
- Validated protocols
- Support/training
- Tool/data interoperability
- Cost-effectiveness
- Regulatory relevance

Other:

Possibility of multiple selection

Is there a new service or tool you wish existed but doesn't yet?

Please write your answer here:

You are welcome to think creatively or describe a need based on your experience

Thank you for completing the FHERITALE questionnaire. Your insights are essential for identifying real service gaps, strengthening research infrastructures, and supporting innovation across the Food, Health, and Environment sectors. The results of this consultation will directly inform the development of thematic service clusters and future actions within the project. If you have any questions or wish to stay informed about the outcomes, please don't hesitate to contact us. Your contribution is truly appreciated.

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.

Figure II-1 summarises the distribution of survey respondents by stakeholder category. The survey reached a wide range of organisations. Most responses come from RIs (40.2 %), with a smaller but significant share from Academic Institutions (11.2 %), and limited input from Industry/Technology Developers (3.0 %) and Civil Society (0.6 %). “Other” ranked the 4.1 %, while missing entries are grouped under “Unspecified” (40.8 %). The RI-heavy composition is valuable for identifying practical needs around access, standardisation, and interoperability of services. The smaller industrial participation suggests an opportunity to deepen engagement with technology providers and SMEs in future survey waves, while the large “Unspecified” share indicates that basic metadata capture (organisation type) should be enforced to improve representativeness and downstream analyses.

As for the geographical distribution, Country labels were canonicalised to ISO 3166 short English names to remove duplicates (e.g., Italia/IT → Italy; Slovenija → Slovenia; Czech Republic → Czechia). The largest contribution was raised from Italy (32.0 %), followed by Romania (10.7 %), with a long tail of EU countries (France – 4.1 %; Slovenia – 2.4 %; Greece – 1.8 %, etc.). The EU-centred footprint aligns with the project scope and is strong enough to support EU-level integration pilots. With Italy and Romania representing over 40% of the sample – explainable also through a higher engagement according to the FHERITALE Beneficiaries in charge for the WP6 task leadership and coordination – early demonstrators (e.g., method development, training, and TNA/ access) can be staged where user density is highest, while maintaining a pan-European dissemination plan to ensure broader adoption.

The age distribution is skewed toward mid-career and senior profiles (50-59 y: 20.1%; 40-49 y - 13.6 %; 30-39 y - 11.8 %), with a non-trivial number of missing entries (43.8 %). The prevalence of experienced researchers typically correlates with demand for validated methods, standard operating procedures (SOPs), and policy-ready evidence. The limited participation of Under-30 respondents is a reminder to broaden outreach (e.g., through graduate programmes and early-career networks), while the high “Unspecified” share suggests enhancing the survey’s mandatory fields or providing clearer data entry guidance.

Respondents were asked whether they are actively involved in RI initiatives. A substantial group responded “True” (39.1 %), a smaller group “False” (20.1 %) and many entries are missing (“Unspecified” - 40.8 %). Capturing a large cohort of RI insiders provides implementation-level insights (access modalities, SOP gaps, data harmonisation needs). The sizable “Unspecified” block is a reminder to stress completeness of critical fields in future rounds. In terms of action, these results support: i) co-designed service menus (method development + cross-domain integration); ii) low-barrier access (TNA, onboarding, helpdesk; iii) standardisation and FAIR-by-design data practices to accelerate reuse and comparability across labs and domains.

Fig.II-1. Distribution of survey respondents by stakeholder category (organisation type, country, age range and active involvement in RI initiatives)

Annex III – Workshop

Figure III-1 and Figure III-2 report the full agenda of the workshop (Fig. III-1: morning session; Fig. III-2: afternoon session).

The morning session was organised as a plenary. After an introduction recalling the FHERITALE project and WP6 objectives and main activities, it was entirely dedicated to stakeholder presentations, with a total of 13 invited contributions from RIs, national agencies, EU-funded projects and research organisations active in the Food-Health-Environment nexus. These presentations covered a wide range of perspectives, including:

- Existing and emerging RI services for monitoring, characterisation and risk assessment of artificial materials
- Cross-domain integration experiences from environmental, food and health research infrastructures
- Challenges related to service accessibility, validation and user engagement
- Lessons learned from sister projects addressing micro- and nanoplastics, sustainable materials and exposure assessment.

This session played a crucial methodological role, as it allowed WP6 participants to situate the survey results within a broader operational and institutional context, and to expose areas of convergence and divergence between service providers and users. Rather than serving as a dissemination exercise, the morning presentations were explicitly conceived as inputs to the subsequent co-creation phase.

The transition to the interactive phase took place at the beginning of the afternoon session. During its introduction, the WP6 team presented:

- An overview of the survey methodology and respondent profile
- Selected preliminary insights related to priority needs, Service Readiness Classification (SRC) levels and frequently reported barriers
- The logical link between the WP6 gap analysis and the subsequent activities planned under Task 6.2, WP7 and WP8

This framing ensured that all participants entered the co-creation sessions with a shared reference framework, while avoiding any premature fixation on conclusions.

In the afternoon, participants were divided into parallel moderated discussion groups. The parallel sessions were organised around three complementary thematic dimensions:

- Priority needs and critical gaps
- Technology and service readiness
- Thematic clustering and actor mapping.

Each group followed a structured moderation guide and worked with visual and operational tools including posters, post-it notes, draft maps and extracts from preliminary survey outputs, to capture inputs systematically. Dedicated participant guides and facilitation materials were prepared in advance and distributed to ensure a shared understanding of objectives and tasks.

During the parallel sessions, participants were encouraged to:

- reflect on the survey findings in light of their own experience

- confirm, challenge or nuance the prioritisation of needs
- identify missing elements, overlooked barriers or emerging opportunities
- discuss how technologies at different SRC levels could realistically evolve into coordinated services.

Moderators actively encouraged participants to articulate not only “what is needed”, but also “why it is difficult” and “under which conditions progress would be feasible”. This focus on feasibility and constraints was critical to avoiding purely aspirational outcomes.

The outputs of each group were documented in real time and subsequently synthesised. Divergent views were not filtered out, but explicitly recorded, as they provide valuable insight into areas where further dialogue, clarification or evidence may be required.

To ensure transparency while respecting the public nature of the deliverable, participant information is reported in aggregated form as summarised in Figure III-3. Overall, the composition of participants ensured balanced representation across domains and sectors, reinforcing the credibility of the validation process.

Figure III-4 shows some photos collected during the workshop, with participants engaged in plenary and parallel discussion sessions.

WORKSHOP

From mapping to action: a co-creation pathway towards gap identification and thematic clustering

22-23 October 2025

Agenda

DAY 1 – October 22 nd	
19:00 – 22:00	Social dinner at Restaurant “Caru’ cu bere”, Stavropoleos 5 Street, Bucharest Old Town
DAY 2 – October 23 rd	
08:45 – 09:15	Registration, IBA Bucharest, 5 Ancuta Baneasa Street
09:15 – 09:45	Welcome and tour de table - Moderator: Gabriel Mustatea (IBA)
09:45 – 10:00	Brief introduction of FHERITALE project (Antonio Rosato, project coordinator)
10:00 – 10:10	WP6 short presentation (Claudia Zoani, ENEA, WP6 leader)
10:10 – 11:10	Stakeholders’ presentations (I) – Moderator: Gabriel Mustatea (IBA)
	<i>Paulina Ramirez Quevedo, EMBRC-ERIC - EMBRC Services For Pollutant Monitoring & Impact Assessment</i>
	<i>Simona LITESCU FILIPESCU, INCDSB - Integrating Research Infrastructure Services Across Domains: Insights from DANUBIUS-RI for Environmental and Societal Well-Being</i>
	<i>Susana Guzman Puyol, CSIC - Sustainable Plastics towards a Circular Economy of the Spanish Research Council – CSIC</i>
	<i>Simona Bianco, RIANA project – Supporting users’ research needs in nanoscience: perspectives from the RIANA project</i>
11.10 – 11.30	Coffee break
11:30 – 14:00	Stakeholders’ presentations (II) – Moderator: Gabriel Mustatea (IBA)
	<i>Ayoub El Ghadraoui, Euro-BioImaging ERIC - Euro-BioImaging services for detecting and characterizing micro- and nanoplastics</i>
	<i>Petru Jitaru, ANSES - Challenges in the determination of TiO₂ (nano)particles in foodstuffs by single particle inductively coupled plasma - mass spectrometry</i>
	<i>Andrea Valsesia, JRC - Co-Creating Solutions: JRC Nanobiotech Lab’s Role in Bridging Service Gaps Through Open Access, Training, and Long-Term Partnerships</i>
	<i>Alexandra Mocanu, IMT Bucharest - Chemical Reconversion: An Innovative Approach for Plastic Recycling and Circularity</i>
	<i>Jan Stránský, Institute of Biotechnology, CAS - Centre of Molecular Structure: Services for structural biology and beyond</i>
	<i>Dalila Fernandes, MIRRI-ERIC - Building Service Capacity for Microbial Research and Innovation: MIRRI-ERIC’s Experience</i>
	<i>Ottavia Burello, D4Pack Project - Build Together to Achieve Common Goal</i>
	<i>Alba Hernández Bonilla – UAB - Health risks of micro- and nanoplastics exposure: Insights from the PlasticHeal Project</i>
<i>Nafsika Papaioannou, National Hellenic Research Foundation - integrated exposome methodology of the ENVESOME project</i>	

Fig.III-2. Bucharest co-creation workshop, 23 October 2025 – Agenda, morning session

14:00 – 15:00	Lunch
15:00 – 16:30	Co-creation process (I) – Moderator: Claudia Zoani (ENEA)
15:00 – 15:10	<i>Instructions for sessions and survey insights</i>
15:10 – 16:30	<i>Co-creation process: Priority needs and critical gaps; Technology and Service readiness; Thematic clustering & Actor mapping (I)</i>
16.30 – 16.50	Coffee break
16:50 – 18:00	Co-creation process (II) – Moderator: Claudia Zoani (ENEA)
16:50 – 17:40	<i>Co-creation process: Priority needs and critical gaps; Technology and Service readiness; Thematic clustering & Actor mapping (II)</i>
17:40 – 18:00	<i>Wrap-up and conclusions</i>

Funded by
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Fig.III-2. Bucharest co-creation workshop, 23 October 2025 – Agenda, afternoon session

Fig.III-3. Bucharest co-creation workshop, 23 October 2025 - Distribution of workshop participants by category (a) and domain (b)

Fig.III-4. Bucharest co-creation workshop, 23 October 2025 - selected photos